

Bandwidth Enhancement in CPW Fed Compact Rectangular Patch Antenna

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Abstract : This paper presents a novel CPW fed patch antenna supporting a wide band from 2.66 GHz - 8.32 GHz. The antenna is compact with size 32 x 30 x 1.6 mm³, built over FR4-epoxy substrate ($\epsilon_r=4.4$). Bandwidth enhancement has been achieved by using the concept of modified ground structure (MGS). For this purpose structural design has been optimised by parametric simulations in CST MWS. The proposed antenna can perform well in variety of wireless communication services including 5.15 GHz- 5.35 GHz and 5.725 GHz- 5.825 GHz WLAN IEEE 802.11 g/a, 5.2/ 5.5/ 5.8 GHz Wi-Fi, 3.5/5.5 WiMax applications and 3.7 - 4.2 GHz C band satellite communications bands. The measured experimental results show that bandwidth (S11 < -10 dB) of antenna is 5.64 GHz. The performance of antenna is studied in terms of reflection coefficient, radiation characteristics, current distribution and gain.

Keywords : Broadband antenna, CPW fed, CST MWS,

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014